

COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE IN REALIZING SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS IN CIBIRU WETAN VILLAGE CILEUNYI DISTRICT BANDUNG REGENCY

Riska Saputri¹, Titin Rohayatin², Lukman Munawar Fauzi³, Dicky Febriansyah Rokhmat⁴

Jenderal Achmad Yani University^{1,2,3,4}

riska.saputri@student.unjani.ac.id¹, titin.rohayatin@lecture.unjani.ac.id²,
lukman.munawar@lecture.unjani.ac.id³,
dicky.febriansyah@lecture.unjani.ac.id⁴

ABSTRACT

This research is motivated by the less than optimal implementation of collaborative governance in increasing village economic growth, this incated by the lack of community participation, the complexity of survey instruments, the lack of maximum communication by the village government regarding the concept of SDGs, the lack of all stakeholders understanding their roles and responsibilities, and the collaboration process is not fully inclusive and synergistic. Problem formulation: how Collaborative Governance in realizing the SDGs as a pillar of economic growth. Research objective: to describe and analyze the implementation of cross-sectoral collaboration in sustainable village development. The theory used by Ansell and Gash, which includes four dimensions: starting conditions, institutional design, facilitative leadership and collaborative processes. A descriptive research method with a qualitative approach was employed. Data collection techniques through literature studies and field studies (observation, interviews, and documentation). Research informants: consists of five pentahelix elements. The results show: (1) the initial conditions faced with resource gaps, low digital literacy, and lack of public understanding of the SDGs, (2) institutional design is seen through formal-informal regulations, but it has not been accompanied by a comprehensive understanding between stakeholders, (3) facilitative leadership can be seen from the active role of village heads in building communication and trust. (4) The collaboration process is carried out through a deliberative forum

Keywords: : collaborative governance, village sdgs, economic growth, pentahelix.

INTRODUCTION

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) or known as *the Sustainable Development Goals* (SDGs), are the result of the ratification of the UN Summit in 2015 which was attended by 193 countries including Indonesia. *The Sustainable Development Goals* (SDGs) are compiled to be a new development milestone for each country, in order to continue *the Millennium Development Goals* (MDGs) to improve people's living standards. Then the (Kurniawan & Artist , 2023)*Sustainable Development Goals* (SDGs) agenda was formed as a global development agreement. Research conducted by (Velby & Yuadi , 2023) said that "the SDGs were born in response to a shared concern to create a just, safe, and sustainable world for all of humanity, for a sustainable environment for current and future generations." The SDGs reflect the moral principle that no one country should be left behind, while others achieve prosperity, every individual and country has a responsibility to contribute to realizing the global vision of the SDGs.(Natalia & Maulidya, 2023).

The simplification of SDGs into Village SDGs provides clear and detailed direction in achieving holistic goals, allowing the Village Government to optimally utilize the potential of existing resources (Rahman & Tarigan, 2020). Village involvement in the grand design of sustainable development goals has the potential to contribute 71%, based on the data presented above. This indicates that the national Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) can be easily achieved if village development is focused on steps that support sustainable development. To achieve success and ensure that the SDGs can provide universal welfare, there are three main pillars as development indicators (Iskandar, 2020).

According to (Iskandar, 2023) "The village as a homepage as well as the backbone of Indonesia's development is an undeniable fact. Villages are the spearhead of the government in carrying out development." This emphasizes the strategic role of villages as the spearhead of the government in carrying out various development programs. Building a village means building Indonesia, building Indonesia from a village. According to Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages, villages have the authority to regulate and manage development in their own areas. The potential of villages in supporting the achievement of the SDGs can be seen through two aspects. First, the regional aspect is based on data from the Ministry of Home Affairs in 2019 that 91% of Indonesia's territory is rural. Thus, village development will contribute 91% to the achievement of ten regionally-oriented national SDGs goals such as clean energy, economic growth, industry and innovation, inequality reduction, climate mitigation, ocean conservation, land conservation, institutions and justice, and development cooperation networks. Second, the population aspect based on the results of data collection from the

Development Village Index (IDM) of the Ministry of Rural Development (IDM) shows that 71% of the Indonesian population is in villages.

Cibiru Wetan Village, Cileunyi District, Bandung Regency is one of the villages in Bandung Regency with the Independent Village category and has achieved the 2nd highest Village Development Index (IDM) in West Java under Panjalu Ciamis Village (Riyandi, 2023). Cibiru Wetan Village has achieved various achievements at the regional, national, and even international levels. Cibiru Wetan Village was selected to represent West Java Province in the ASEAN Village Network in the Digital Village category in 2023 2023 (Faiz, 2023), Cibiru Wetan Village was also a pilot anti- corruption village in 2022 by the Indonesian Corruption Eradication Committee (Fitriana, 2022), and Cibiru Wetan Village also won 1st place in the regional II national village competition in 2022 (Hasyim, 2022).

Cibiru wetan Village is one of the villages that implements the *smart village concept* which is a program from the Ministry of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions and Transmigration of the Republic of Indonesia (Kemendes PDTT RI). *Smart Village* is a solution and innovative initiative to accelerate development in the village. This program aims to improve welfare and quality of life by utilizing technology in various aspects of development. The (Iskandar, 2023)*smart village program* initiated by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development also emphasizes the concept of *Smart People*, which is a center and source of knowledge information needed by the community. In addition, there is *Smart Governance*, which assists the Village Government in implementing *e- governance*, as well as providing transparent and accountable public services. Furthermore, *Smart Economy* aims to increase community participation in productive economic activities to accelerate economic growth and village welfare. Finally, (Iskandar, 2023) *Smart Living* invites villagers to create a healthy, beautiful, and clean environment. This initiative is one of the tangible forms of implementation of the SDGs.

The implementation of the Village SDGs by Cibiru Wetan Village on the way to realizing the sustainable development goals of Cibiru Wetan Village is still experiencing challenges. This can be seen from the SDGs status of Cibiru Wetan Village has a score of 58.95 taken from the average score of 18 village SDGs goals, the scale of the Village SDGs score is 0-100 the larger the score shows the achievement of the Village SDGs goals. The SDGs pillars that have the highest scores include SDGs point 5 related to Village Women's Involvement with a score of 89.12 and SDGs point 7 related to clean and renewable energy villages with a

score of 99.73. On the other hand, the pillars that have a low score include SDGs point 8 related to Village Economic Growth with a score of 27.47. (SID Ministry of Villages, 2024)

Figure 1. Score SDGs Desa Cibiru Wetan Village

Source: Village Information System of The Ministry of Village, 2024

Table 1. Achievement of SDGs Indicators of Economic Growth Pillar Village in Cibiru Wetan Village in 2024

Indicator	Achievements of Cibiru Wetan Village	Target SDGs	Status
Population	19,370 people	-	-
PDB per Kapita	IDR 281,227	> IDR 30,000,000	Not Achieved
Formal Sector (estimate)	Mostly informal	> 51% sektor formal	Not Achieved
Access to Capital for MSMEs	Data not available	> 51% of MSMEs have access to	Unknown

Unemployment Rate	The number of users is 7,271. Open unemployment rate: 63.77%	0%	Not Achieved
-------------------	--	----	--------------

Source: Processed Researcher, 2025

Based on this data, calculated from the total village income of IDR 3,168,787,000 and the additional turnover of BUMDes of IDR 2,278,515,898, the total approximation value of Cibiru Wetan Village is IDR 5,447,302,898. With a population of 19,370 people, the value of the village's GDP per capita only reaches around IDR 281,227, still very far from the target of IDR 30 million per capita set in the SDGs of the Village Pillar of Economic Growth.

In addition, the formal sector in this village is still dominated by informal jobs such as farm laborers, small self-employed people, and day laborers. The unemployment rate is also still there, while MSMEs' access to formal financing and the contribution of the tourism sector to the village economy has not been comprehensively documented. This condition shows that there is a considerable gap between the actual conditions and the ideal conditions expected in the Village SDGs. Therefore, strategic steps are needed, such as economic empowerment based on local potential, strengthening the MSME sector, expanding access to finance, increasing the skills of the new workforce, and optimizing the tourism sector to accelerate the achievement of equitable and sustainable village economic growth.

According to Ansell and Gash (in Greenwood et al., 2021), collaborative governance is a method of government management involving non-governmental or state actors, focusing on context and deliberation in a collaborative decision-making process to implement public policies and programs. This method emerged in the governance era, during the transition from the Old Public Administration (OPA) paradigm to the New Public Management (NPM) paradigm. Governance can be simply understood as a change in the implementation of public policy that involves not only the government but also other actors, such as the public and private sectors. The importance of governance involves individuals involved in decision-making, because the problems faced often make the decision-making and implementation process more complex (Dwiyanto, 2021). Collaborative governance focuses on public policies and issues, emerging from the desire to collaborate in resolving public problems or

conflicts, thus involving many parties (Maulia & Setiyono, 2023) The implementation of *sustainable development goals* (SDGs) in Cibiru Wetan Village, there are several problems that can be analyzed using *collaborative governance theory* according to Ansell and Gash through four main dimensions, namely, initial conditions, institutional design, facilitative leadership and collaboration processes. First, the initial condition of low public understanding of the concept of SDGs.

This affects the level of community participation in SDGs-based development programs, such as filling out questionnaires provided. The survey instruments compiled by the Ministry of Rural Development are too complex and difficult for rural communities to understand, which ultimately results in inaccurate data. In addition, the public's lack of understanding of the goals and benefits of the SDGs causes collaboration between citizens and *other stakeholders* to be less effective. Second, institutional design shows that problems arise from differences in understanding of roles and responsibilities between various *stakeholders* involved in cooperation. Sometimes, even though the existing regulations are quite clear, implementation on the ground still faces obstacles due to a lack of uniform understanding among the actors involved.

Third, Facilitative Leadership has shown good achievements, as evidenced by various awards that have been achieved, one of which is an award from the *ASEAN Village Network* in the Digital Village category. This achievement reflects the ability of the village head to build innovation and develop village potential, which should be a strong foundation to support the optimization of the achievement of *the Sustainable Development Goals* (SDGs) in Cibiru Wetan Village. However, this achievement has not been fully balanced by the high participation of the community in village development. This shows that the village head has not fully succeeded in building community trust as an important element in *collaborative governance*. Fourth, the collaboration process that takes place is not fully inclusive and synergistic. The involvement of actors from the five *elements of pentahelix* is still sectoral and has not been integrated into a comprehensive village development strategy. In addition, there is still a lack of a systematic evaluation mechanism in assessing the extent to which this collaborative program has a real impact on the village economy. Some indicators of success are still short-term without a clear long-term measurement tool, in addition, although there are sustainability initiatives, such as economic digitalization and strengthening village business capacity, there are still challenges in ensuring that programs continue to run despite a change of leadership in the village or the end of cooperation with

external parties.

Based on the problems that have been explained above, in this study the researcher is interested in conducting more in-depth research related to *collaborative governance* in realizing the Village SDGs in Cibiru Wetan Village with research limitations, namely researching related to the implementation of *collaborative governance* in realizing the pillars of village economic growth by raising the title "*Collaborative governance in realizing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in Cibiru Wetan Village, Cileunyi District, Bandung Regency*"

METHOD

The collaborative governance *model* is a method of decision-making, as Ansell and Gash say in that (Noor) Et Al. , 2022) *collaborative governance* is a public policy formulation technique, the process of which is carried out by consensus. Furthermore, Ansell and Gash also described the actors involved in the *collaborative governance process* such as the government, the community, the private sector, non-governmental institutions, academics and the media. The following is Ansell and Gash's concept of *collaborative governance modeling*:

Figure 2. Type Collaborative Governance

Source: Ansell and Gash in (Noor) Et Al. , 2022)

Based on the image above, Ansel and Gash have divided the five dimensions of *collaborative governance* including initial conditions, institutional design, facilitative leadership and collaboration processes.

The research will be carried out by the researcher using a descriptive

qualitative method *with a qualitative approach was employed. Data collection techniques through literature studies and field studies (observation, interviews, and documentation).* because this research aims to describe the existing phenomenon related to *collaborative governance* in realizing the Village SDGs carried out by the Cibiru Wetan Village Government, Cileunyi District, Bandung Regency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It has been a long time since villages have been respected, as a unit of the legal community and have the authority to govern themselves based on the principle of subsidiarity. Monumental policies for villages are constructed in Law Number 6 of 2014. The implementation of Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages became the starting point for the implementation of the development paradigm from the lowest level of government, the village. This is the right paradigm, because sociologically, the majority of the population with all their problems are in the village, and one of the village autonomy policies is intended to excite the local economy and the livelihood of the village community.

In the context of sustainable development, villages have a central role in achieving the *Sustainable Development Goals* (SDGs). Empowered and self-reliant villages can drive economic growth, reduce inequality, and increase resilience to climate change. Cibiru Wetan Village, is one of the villages that is trying to implement the principles of the SDGs in its local development. With the potential of natural and social resources, this village continues to develop various empowerment programs, especially through Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) as well as the active role of community groups such as women and village youth.

Collaboration in an effort to realize *the Sustainable Development Goals* (SDGs) of the village at the point of village economic growth aims to create an inclusive, sustainable, and competitive village economy. Through the *Collaborative Governance approach*, cooperation between the village government, the community, the private sector, and various other stakeholders is expected to improve the economic welfare of the community, open up business and employment opportunities, and strengthen the local economic ecosystem. In addition, this collaboration also plays a role in optimizing the use of village resources, increasing human resource capacity, and developing economic innovations based on local potential, so as to encourage sustainable economic growth in Cibiru Wetan Village.

Starting Conditions

The village government implements a pentahelix-based collaboration, which involves five main elements: government, academia, the business world, communities, and the media. This collaboration is applied in the sustainable development of the village economy. The Head of the Government Section emphasized: "We also apply pentahelix collaboration by involving various parties in the sustainable development of the village economy." (Interview Transcript - Head of Government Section).

Figure 3. Village Government Approach in Collaboration for Achieving Village SDGs

Source: Author's analysis using NVivo 12 Plus, 2025

The imbalance of resources is one of the challenges in the collaboration process in Cibiru Wetan Village. Although villages have the initiative to carry out SDGs-based development, limitations in terms of funding and technology remain obstacles that must be overcome. As in the aspect of technology development, to overcome the limitations of digital access, the village collaborated with PT. Telkom in the procurement of internet networks. In addition, UNPAD KKN students also contributed to developing a digital-based marketing system for local MSMEs. The lack of public understanding of digital technology is one of the main challenges. Therefore, UNPAD KKN students held digital training to improve people's technological literacy.

The Village Government Approach in SDGs Collaboration is a strategy applied to create inclusive, sustainable, and community-oriented village development at large. This collaboration involves various stakeholders so that

development programs can run effectively and achieve sustainable development goals (SDGs) at the village level. This approach is based on several main principles that guide its implementation, namely, the Basis of Common Interest, the Basis of Equality and Openness, and Prioritizing Pentahelix Collaboration.

The implementation of *the pentahelix* concept in realizing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the pillar of economic growth in Cibiru Wetan Village has not been running optimally. Collaboration between actors including village governments, the private sector, academics, communities, and the media is not formed as a synergistic unit. Each actor tends to work partially and does not have enough knowledge about the involvement of the other actors. For example, the cooperation carried out between the village government and PT. Ambhara through BUMDes is not known by elements of the media, academics, or the community. This ignorance between actors shows the weakness of coordination and communication in collaborations that should be integrated. These unfavorable initial conditions are fundamental obstacles in building trust, facilitating open communication, and encouraging the creation of effective collaboration processes as required in the *collaborative governance* model. If the initial conditions are not handled properly, then collaboration tends to be formal, fragmentative, and does not produce the synergy between the parties necessary to achieve a common goals.

Facilitative Leadership

Regarding the dimension of facilitative leadership in the implementation of *collaborative governance* in Cibiru Wetan Village, based on the results of observations, facilitative leadership implemented by the Head of Cibiru Wetan Village is an important key in the smooth operation of cooperation between parties in the village. The village head not only makes decisions, but also actively facilitates the collaboration process so that it runs effectively. The village head plays the role of a mediator who maintains a balance between interests, resolves obstacles that arise, and builds trust between partners, such as BUMDes, PKK, Farmer Women's Groups, KKN students, the private sector and the media. In various village discussion forums, the village head ensures that all parties have space to convey opinions, ideas, and obstacles. This open and participatory atmosphere reflects transparent and inclusive leadership practices, where decisions are made jointly and by agreement.

"As the village head, of course, I try to create open communication with all parties, both the community, partners, and related institutions. We hold regular meetings to convey the progress of cooperation and accommodate the aspirations of

all parties. With transparent communication and inclusive discussions, we can prevent misunderstandings and build trust in cooperation." (Village Head)

Apart from that, the village government also always holds discussion forums such as village deliberations, coordination meetings and workshops involving various elements including partners. Each party has an equal opportunity to express their opinions and input, which will then be considered in decision-making.

The village head is also active in directing cooperation to suit the needs of the village. The village head not only facilitates, but also provides concrete guidance so that the programs carried out really have an impact on the community. This approach shows that leadership in Cibiru Wetan is not rigid, but responsive and solution-oriented. The leadership role of the village head makes collaboration in the village run smoother and more sustainable. The role of the village head as a facilitator not only strengthens the relationship between parties, but also encourages the achievement of village development that is more strategic and beneficial to the community at large.

Facilitative leadership in Cibiru Wetan Village plays an important role in ensuring that cooperation between stakeholders runs effectively. The village head acts as a mediator who maintains a balance of interests, prevents conflicts, and builds trust among cooperation partners. In discussion forums, the village government provides space for various parties, such as BUMDes, PKK, Farmer Women Groups, KKN students, and private partners, to convey ideas and obstacles faced. With a transparent and participatory approach, village heads ensure that every decision is taken in an inclusive and consensus-based manner. This creates a more dynamic collaborative environment, allows for program sustainability, and increases the positive impact on economic growth and the welfare of rural communities.

Institutional Design

The Cibiru Wetan Village Government has implemented a structured and effective institutional design in supporting *collaborative governance*. The two main aspects that were emphasized, namely clear rules of the game and openness and transparency, seemed to be going well. The rules of the game used include, formal regulations are implemented through a *Memorandum of Understanding* (MoU) or cooperation agreement. This document regulates the rights, obligations, and contributions of each party, both from the village government, BUMDes, the community, and private partners. The clarity of these rules helps prevent conflicts and facilitate cooperation coordination.

Meanwhile, informal regulations such as a culture of mutual cooperation, deliberation, and regular communication both in person and through *online* media serve to strengthen synergy and ensure that decisions are made collectively. Program information is also conveyed openly through village deliberations, *websites*, social media, and bulletin boards, which provide space for public participation and supervision.

In addition, the village government also conducts periodic evaluations to monitor the progress of the program, resolve obstacles, and ensure that targets are achieved. This evaluation process is carried out from the beginning of the cooperation to the final stage, showing a commitment to adaptive and results-based governance. Overall, the institutional design in Cibiru Wetan Village is able to create open, clear, and sustainable cooperation. This proves that the *principle of collaborative governance* has been implemented in a real way and supports the achievement of village development goals.

With clear rules of the game and openness in every institutional process, the Cibiru Wetan Village Government shows its commitment to implementing the principles of *effective collaborative governance*. Through structured cooperation mechanisms, periodic evaluations, and transparency in decision-making, villages are able to build trust among stakeholders. This approach not only ensures that each program runs in accordance with the village development vision, but also encourages active participation from communities and cooperative partners. Thus, the collaboration that exists can run sustainably and provide real benefits for the progress of Cibiru Wetan Village.

Collaboration Process

This process focuses not only on achieving the end goal, but also on the dynamics of cooperation that build the foundation of sustainability in *collaborative governance*. There are five main aspects in the collaboration process, namely face-to-face forums, consensus-based dialogue, building trust between actors, sustainability of activities, and *intermediate outcomes*.

One of the face-to-face forums conducted by Cibiru Wetan Village is the village deliberation. The village deliberations in Cibiru Wetan Village were carried out in an inclusive manner, where all elements of society were given the same opportunity to express their opinions, aspirations, and obstacles faced. Every stakeholder, actively participates in discussions that take place openly. In a collaborative forum involving two or more parties, deliberation is the main foundation in building

understanding and uniting interests. This process is not just for the submission of opinions, but a strategic space to elaborate ideas, clarify roles and responsibilities, and formulate decisions born from mutual agreement so that it reflects collective commitment.

This forum is not only a medium for planning, but also an effective problem-solving instrument. When obstacles or dynamics of cooperation arise, the forum becomes a place to study the problem objectively and formulate solutions that can be accepted by all parties, thus the deliberative forum not only maintains the sustainability of the program, but also strengthens cohesion and trust between the actors involved. The success of this forum lies in an open, participatory, and sustainable process. The synergy formed is not the result of chance, but the product of a structured and directed collaborative mechanism. This is what makes face-to-face forums a driving force for effective collaboration in village development.

Consensus-based dialogue, in Cibiru Wetan Village, decision-making is carried out through a consensus-based dialogue approach, which prioritizes consensus deliberation and active involvement of all stakeholders. Forums such as village deliberations are strategic spaces to express opinions, unite aspirations, and build decisions that are fair and acceptable to all parties. PKK, the Farmer Women's Group (KWT), and other partners were not only invited as participants, but were given equal space to voice their needs and propose solutions. This approach makes each policy more contextual, on target, and in favor of the interests of the wider community, especially vulnerable groups such as mothers and women farmers.

Although the process of reaching consensus often faces challenges, such as differences in interests between actors and lack of participation from some parties, the Village Government overcomes it by opening communication regularly, both through formal forums and informal meetings. The decisions taken are also always based on data and field facts to maintain objectivity and acceptance. Trust is an important foundation in this process. Each party believes that honest, open, and responsible collaboration will result in sustainable policies. This strengthens the synergy between actors, and becomes an important social capital in encouraging the achievement of the sustainable development goals (SDGs) at the village level. Trust in SDGs collaboration is realized through the active involvement of the community in every program carried out. Community participation is not only limited to beneficiaries, but also as the main actor in the implementation of the program. With this approach, the information disseminated really has a real impact on the progress of the village.

Trust is the main key in establishing successful cooperation to support the achievement of the SDGs in Cibiru Wetan Village. The village government not only involves the community as beneficiaries, but also as active implementers in village programs. This builds a sense of belonging and strengthens the relationship between the community and the village government. The Community Information Group (KIM) plays a role in conveying information that really has an impact and involves residents in the process. That way, the community feels appreciated and has more trust in every program that is carried out.

The village government is also a liaison between various parties such as companies, campuses, and local governments. For example, cooperation with PT Telkom for village internet, as well as PT Ambhara Duta Santi through BUMDes, is carried out by understanding each other's roles and commitments. The private sector and KKN students from UNPAD emphasized the importance of open communication and joint evaluation so that cooperation runs well. However, there are still challenges such as low digital literacy and difficulty adjusting activity schedules, especially for MSME and KWT actors who are elderly. However, the village government continues to maintain trust by opening a space for dialogue, providing information openly, and involving all parties in the process. This is what keeps the collaboration maintained and has a real impact on the people of Cibiru Wetan Village.

In addition, trust is also built through the active involvement of various parties in every collaboration process. The village government not only plays the role of a director, but also a facilitator who ensures that each partner has room to contribute. Through information transparency, open communication, and commitment to implementing agreements, collaboration between village governments and stakeholders can run well. This trust that has been established is an important foundation in creating sustainable cooperation and providing real benefits to the people of Cibiru Wetan Village, with this trust maintained, every program that is carried out is not only on target, but also easier to accept and support by all levels of society.

The sustainability of the program in Cibiru Wetan Village is supported by various parties. The village government ensures that there is coaching and assistance so that the program runs in the long term. BUMDesa continues to innovate and look for cooperation opportunities to develop village businesses. UNPAD KKN students help build a digital ecosystem and utilize e-commerce platforms to support marketing. The Women Farmers Group maintains sustainability through training, land use, and a more efficient distribution system. The PKK Mobilization Team

ensures that the program continues to run by involving the community and providing assistance in entrepreneurship and marketing of local products. Meanwhile, PT. AMBARADUTASATI plays a role in marketing, innovation, and technology assistance. With cooperation between the village government, the community, academics, and the private sector, programs in Cibiru Wetan Village can continue to grow and provide long-term benefits to the community.

Sustainable development in the economic sector at the village scale has an important role in improving the welfare of the community in the long term. In the context of villages, economic development focuses not only on increasing income, but also on creating an independent, inclusive, and sustainable economic system. This includes optimal use of local resources, community capacity building through training and mentoring, and the use of technology to expand market access

Sustainable economic development in Cibiru Wetan Village is very important to improve the welfare of the community in the long term. The Village Head emphasized the optimization of local potential through BUMDes, Women Farmer Groups, and MSMEs, as well as encouraging digitalization so that the village economy is more independent. This is supported by the Head of Village Government who emphasizes the need for transparent policies with a sustainable impact.

The ongoing efforts of UNPAD Community Service Program (KKN) students in building a digital ecosystem in Cibiru Wetan Village. Through initiatives such as creating standing banners containing information about digitalization and providing digital booklets that can be accessed anytime by the community, the KKN students succeeded in creating an information platform that remains relevant even after the KKN program has ended. Collaborating with banks to create QRIS and use digital platforms like Shopee adds a dimension of the program's purpose, enabling the village to continue utilizing technology to support economic growth and facilitate access for the community. This initiative reflects the use of technology for poverty programs, improving digital literacy, and providing long-term impacts for the village community.

The Director of BUMDes emphasized the importance of BUMDes' role in creating a sustainable village economy. Focusing on local potential, innovation, capacity building, and collaboration with partners demonstrates a strategy that supports village economic independence. This ensures that businesses not only provide short-term benefits but also can survive and thrive in the long term. The diversity of businesses developed not only supports the local economy but also

contributes to job creation and increased community income.

Based on data from the 2024 Mawa Raharja BUMDesa Profile, a significant growth trend is evident in the management of village business units. In the four years since its establishment in 2021, BUMDesa's turnover increased sharply from IDR 343 million in the first year to over IDR 2.2 billion in 2023, before experiencing a slight decline to IDR 2.12 billion in 2024. This surge in turnover reflects BUMDesa's active role in building the local economy through diverse business units, such as tourism management, artesian wells, IT providers, waste management, and trade partnerships. Village capital participation has also remained consistent, ranging from IDR 50 million to IDR 70 million per year, demonstrating the village government's commitment to promoting the sustainability of village economic enterprises. Furthermore, the contribution of Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) to Village Original Income (PADes) has also shown a positive trend, increasing from IDR 6.8 million in 2021 to IDR 30 million in 2024. This increase reflects the increased effectiveness of BUMDes institutions in managing village economic resources productively.

Grafik 1. Development of Turnover, Capital, and PADES, BUMDes Cibiru Wetan 2021-2024

Source: Cibiru Wetan BUMDes Profile Document, 2024

This data confirms that BUMDes Mawa Raharja plays a strategic role in driving economic growth in Cibiru Wetan Village. However, achieving sustainable and inclusive economic growth, as outlined in the SDGs, requires institutional strengthening, diversification of funding sources, and closer integration between BUMDes and other village development programs.

The Director of BUMDes and UNPAD KKN students highlighted the role of innovation and digitalization in strengthening the village economy, such as the use of the digital financial system and online marketing. Meanwhile, the Chairman of the PKK Mobilization Team and the Farmer Women Group emphasized the importance of entrepreneurship training and financial literacy for women to be more economically independent. Private partners such as PT. AMBARADUTASATI also sees that village economic development must be based on local needs with technological support and business assistance. Overall, village economic development requires cooperation between the government, the community, academia, and the private sector so that it can continue to develop and provide long-term benefits.

Overall, the implementation of Collaborative Governance in realizing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in Cibiru Wetan Village, particularly in the economic growth pillar, has shown positive progress in empowering communities and promoting local economic growth. The pentahelix approach has been able to build the initial foundation for more inclusive and sustainable development collaboration. The village government plays an active role as a facilitator, maintaining communication, opening up spaces for consensus-building dialogue, and implementing the principles of transparency and accountability at every stage of the collaboration.

However, based on an analysis of the four dimensions of Collaborative Governance according to Ansell and Gash initial conditions, institutional design, facilitative leadership, and collaboration processes it was found that the implementation of pentahelix collaboration in Cibiru Wetan Village still faces several fundamental challenges. The collaboration that occurs tends to be sectoral and has not been integrated into an inclusive and sustainable multi-stakeholder forum. Limitations in resource imbalances, weak cross-sectoral institutional design, and the lack of optimal face-to-face forums between actors are factors that hinder building trust, coordination, and collaborative synergy.

Contains descriptive statistical results, assumption tests, and analysis. Tables and/or images must be meaningful and easy to understand and should be placed at the end of the manuscript, not in the text. In qualitative research, direct quotes from interviews with informants are not used. Explains the research results and discussions supported by appropriate theories, as well as research limitations.

To clarify the discussion, the author can use tables or images. The table number and title are written in the center above the table, while the figure number

and title are written in the center below the figure. This can be seen more clearly in the example below.

CONCLUSION

The implementation of Collaborative Governance in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly in the pillar of economic growth in Cibiru Wetan Village, demonstrates a strong synergy among key stakeholders through a pentahelix approach. This collaboration focuses on empowering UMKM, optimizing local resources, and enhancing community capacity. Although initial challenges included disparities in resources, limited access to technology, and low public awareness of the SDGs, a participatory approach and facilitative leadership by the village head have successfully fostered effective cooperation supported by both formal and informal institutional frameworks grounded in local values such as mutual cooperation (*gotong royong*). Deliberative forums and digital communication channels have enhanced stakeholder engagement, resulting in increased UMKM digitalization, improved village-owned enterprises (BUMDes), strengthened agricultural productivity, and the formation of women-led community-based economic groups. To ensure the sustainability of this collaborative model, it is essential to strengthen cross-sectoral coordination by appointing sector-specific Persons In Charge (PIC), conduct regular evaluations through multi-stakeholder forums, and organize digital literacy training programs for residents and entrepreneurs with the involvement of universities, community groups, and private entities. These efforts are expected to further advance inclusive and sustainable rural economic development.

REFERENCES

- Dwiyanto, A. (2021). *Mewujudkan Good Governance Melalui Pelayanan Publik*. UGM PRESS.
- Faiz, M. (2023, July 26). *Program Desa Digital Binaan Bank BJB Dibawa ke ASEAN Village Network*. DetikJabar. <https://www.detik.com/jabar/berita/d-6842069/program-desa-digital-binaan-bank-bjb-dibawa-ke-asean-village-network>
- Fitriana, S. N. (2022, November 29). *Desa Cibiru Wetan di Kabupaten Bandung Jadi Contoh Desa Antikorupsi*. DetikJabar. <https://www.detik.com/jabar/jabar-gaskeun/d-6433134/desa-cibiru-wetan-di-kabupaten-bandung-jadi-contoh-desa-antikorupsi>
- Greenwood, S., Singer, L., & Willis, W. (2021). *Collaborative Governance: Principles,*

- Process, and Practical Tools*. Routledge.
- Hasyim, L. I. (2022, November 24). *Desa Cibiru Wetan dan Kelurahan Bintara Sabet Gelar Juara Lomdeskel Tingkat Regional Tahun 2022*. Radarkuningan.Com. <https://radarkuningan.disway.id/read/651175/desa-cibiru-wetan-dan-kelurahan-bintara-sabet-gelar-juara-lomdeskel-tingkat-regional-tahun-2022>
- Iskandar, H. (2020). *SDGs desa : percepatan pencapaian tujuan pembangunan nasional berkelanjutan* (Pertama). Yayasan Pustaka Obor Indonesia.
- Iskandar, H. (2023). *Bahasa dan Diskursus Kebangkitan Desa* (M. Afifuddin, Ach. F. Suja'ie, & I. Augusta, Eds.). Penerbit Buku Kompas.
- Kurniawan, M. R., & Artisa, R. A. (2023). STRATEGI PENINGKATAN PARTISIPASI MASYARAKAT DALAM PERENCANAAN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS (SDGs) DESA. STUDI KASUS: DESA CIBURIAL, KECAMATAN CIMENYAN, KABUPATEN BANDUNG, JAWA BARAT. *Inovasi Pembangunan: Jurnal Kelitbangan*.
- Maulia, E. I., & Setiyono, B. (2023). COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE DALAM PENGEMBANGAN DESA WISATA NGLANGGERAN: ANALISIS DAMPAK DIGITALISASI DESA WISATA. *Journal UNDIP*, 1-15. www.fisip.undip.ac.id
- Natalia, A., & Maulidya, E. N. (2023). Aktualisasi Empat Pilar Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Di Perdesaan Kecamatan Natar Kabupaten Lampung Selatan. *JlIP: Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Pemerintahan*, 8(1), 21-41. <https://doi.org/10.14710/jiip>
- Noor, M., Suaedi, F., & Mardiyanta, A. (2022). *COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE Suatu Tinjauan Teoritis dan Praktik* (M. R. Firdaus & F. Z. Yopiannor, Eds.; 1st ed.). BILDUNG.
- Rahman, F., & Tarigan, J. S. R. (2020). *Inovasi Pemerintahan: Menuju Tata Kola Pemerintahan Daerah Ideal* (1st ed.). Intrans Publishing.
- Riyandi, R. (2023, July 21). *4 Desa di Kabupaten Bandung Masuk 10 Besar Desa dengan IDM Tertinggi Se-Jawa Barat*. Ayobandung.Com. <https://www.ayobandung.com/bandung-raya/799544584/4-desa-di-kabupaten-bandung-masuk-10-besar-desa-dengan-idm-tertinggi-se-jawa-barat>
- SID Kemendesa. (2024, June 12). *SDGs Desa: Pencarian Data*. Sid.Kemendesa.Go.Id. <https://sid.kemendesa.go.id/sdgs>
- Velby, A. C., & Yuadi, I. (2023). META-ANALITIK COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE DALAM PEMBANGUNAN BERKELANJUTAN. *J-3P (Jurnal Pembangunan Pemberdayaan Pemerintahan)*, 8(1), 19-41. <https://doi.org/10.33701/j-3p.v8i1.3455>